

Methodology to Characterize Ply-Ply and Tool-Ply Friction for Aligned Discontinuous Fiber Prepregs

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Introduce TuFF

- **Chopped fibers are aligned** by water flow onto a film
- Films of aligned fiber are prepregged with resin
- Prepreg can be used in **thermoforming process**
 - **Allows for stretch** during forming
 - Final properties comparable to continuous UD prepreg

Role of Numerical Model

- **Goal:** Develop tool to:
 - Guide geometry and process conditions to minimize failed parts.
 - Maximize manufacturing rate.
- **Modeling optimizes process** without spending material, energy, labor.
- **Develop and validate** model's prediction of deformation, failure criteria.

Constitutive Equation

- Developed a model that **matches uniaxial extension data**
- Constitutive equation:
 - Viscous equation with strain softening component

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{12} \end{bmatrix} = \eta_P \cdot \begin{bmatrix} D_{11}C_{11} & C_{12} & 0 \\ C_{12} & C_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & C_{66} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\epsilon}_{11} \\ \dot{\epsilon}_{22} \\ \dot{\gamma}_{12} \end{bmatrix}$$

Stresses = Polymer viscosity · Directional magnification from fibers · Strain rates

Ply-Ply Interface

- Constitutive equation:

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Stresses = Polymer viscosity · Directional magnification from fibers · Strain rates

- Transverse strain (ϵ_T)**

- Resisted by higher viscosity of plies in other directions through interface.

- For example, regions of localized ϵ_T have developed around low ply-ply friction

Ply-Ply Interface

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- Shearing/ fiber reorientation

- Rotation of fibers in shearing toward direction of stretch further resisted by interface.

Tool-Ply Interface

- **Tool-ply interface affects balance of translation and deformation**
- **No tool-ply slip** → displacement into mold entirely from material deformation
- **Tool-ply slip** → less material deformation during displacement
 - Less strain localizations
 - Material can bunch/wrinkle
- Predicting tool-ply slip helps optimize forming conditions to minimize tears and wrinkles

- **Displacement**

Forming around a tool radius

All slip:

d_{slip}

All stretch:

Role in Search for Process Conditions

- Changing process conditions will affect friction at interfaces.

Going to higher rate, temperature in forming window.

$T, \dot{\epsilon}$
 Temperature, strain rate
 μ
 Friction coefficient

- Need to characterize to predict deformation, failure criteria

Measuring Friction Coefficient

- **Goal:** Design experimental set-up to measure friction coefficients

- **Test parameters:**

- Ply-ply & tool-ply friction (μ)
- Pressure (P)
- Temperature (T)
- Pulling rate (U)
- Ply orientation ($0^\circ, 90^\circ$)

- **General set up:** TuFF mounted on sides of foil which is pulled through at constant U

$$F^{net} = F_p - 2F_f = 0, \text{ where } F_f = \mu N$$

$$\rightarrow \mu = \frac{F_p}{2N}$$

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Fixture Design

- **Goal:** measure tool-ply friction
- **Context:** prevent TuFF from stretching to isolate friction

Fixture features in literature: Pulling prepreg vs pulling foil (tool-ply friction)

Figure from Sachs et al (2024)

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Figure from Sachs et al (2024)

Our design

Fixture Design

- **Goal:** measure tool-ply friction
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Fixture features in literature: local heating vs oven

Figure from Sachs et al. (2024)

Fixture mounted in oven for isothermal heating

Our design

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Fixture features in literature: Pneumatics vs spring pressure application

Figure from Sachs et al. (2024)

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Fixture features in literature: Pull out vs pull through & rigid plate vs foil

- **Benefits:**
 - Reduced deformation due to entry effects → isolates friction behavior
 - Constant contact area → constant P means simpler μ calculation
 - Pulling foil reduces alignment sensitivity

Fixture Design

Fixture in oven

Fixture Design

Front view: fixed plate

Side view

Fixture in oven

Fixture Design

Front view: fixed plate

Side view

Instron grip

Steel foil

Thermocouples

Fixture in oven

Experiment Setup

1. Mount sample on contact plate using adhesive and clamps

2. Bolt contact plates to pressure plates

3. Insert alignment shafts of movable plate into bearings of fix plate.

4. Compress springs to apply pressure to sample and metal foil

Fixture Design: Wedge

- **Preliminary test procedure:**
 1. Oven/fixture heated
 2. open oven to clamp sample
 3. allow oven temp to restabilize
 - Time for oven temp to stabilize varied
 - Increased set up time per sample
- **Solution:** close oven remotely using wedge
 - Decreased variability in set up
 - Reduced time between tests

Fixture Design: Wedge

- **Features:**

Angled surface for gradual pressure release

Holes for cords

Teflon tape on both sides to decrease friction

Flat surface to avoid point loading

Location of wedge in set-up

Fixture Design: Wedge

- Features:

Wedge pulled out
of fixture to release
pressure

Fixture Design: Wedge

- Features:

**Cords attached to wedge,
threaded through top and
bottom of oven**
→ Remove wedge
while oven is closed

Methodology

- **Goals:**
 1. Verify that fixture measures friction coefficient with **low variability**.
 2. Identify friction's sensitivity to **duration under pressure**.
- **Approach:** Measure tool-ply friction under two pressure durations, with repeat tests.
- **Test Conditions:**
 - Material: TuFF IM7/977-3
 - Temperature: $T = 40^{\circ}\text{C}$
 - Rate: $U = 5 \frac{\text{mm}}{\text{min}}$
 - Pressure: $P = 50 \text{ kPa}$
 - Orientation: 0°
 - Time under pressure before test: $t = [10 \text{ sec}, 4 \text{ min}]$

Forming

Clamped region

Fixture in oven

Results

- **Test 1 & 2:** sample clamped for 10 s before test start
- **Test 3 & 4:** sample clamped for 4 min before test start

Test	Friction Coefficients
1	1.41
2	1.48
3	1.42
4	1.26
Average	1.39
Std Dev	0.10

4 tests at 50kPa, 40°C, and 5mm/min pulling rate
clamped at 10s and 4min before starting test

Results

- Low variability between tests
- No observed dependence on time under pressure at low P, T, U

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1	1.41
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4 tests at 50kPa, 40°C, and 5mm/min pulling rate
clamped at 10s and 4min before starting test

Observations

Samples before test

Samples after test show deformation resulting from shear at glue-sample interface

Resin residue left on metal foil from test

- Indicates uniform pressure application
- Suggest lubricated friction initially
- Increased interfacial adhesion/drag?

Results

- All samples deformed at glue interface
 - Test 4 deformed more than others
 - Worse adhesive bonding resulted in force lost to glue shearing

Test	Friction Coefficients
1	1.41
2	1.48
3	1.42
4	1.26
Average	1.43
Std Dev	0.04

4 tests at 50kPa, 40°C, and 5mm/min pulling rate
clamped at 10s and 4min before starting test

Conclusions

- ✓ Fixture works to measure coefficient with low variability
- ✓ Fixture applied uniform pressure to samples
- ✓ TuFF did not stretch
- For future tests:
 - Time under pressure not a major factor at low P , T and U conditions
 - Potential factor at high T when resin viscosity increases
 - Change adhesive to prevent glue shearing
 - More resistant to shear at high T
- Characterize tool-ply and ply-ply friction coefficients

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